

Study on the Emission of Radon from Some Building Materials

Aye Aye Hnin^{*}, Zin Oo Hlaing^{**}, Thae` Theint Theint Aung^{***}, Thinzar Wut Yee^{****}

Abstract

The emission of the amount of indoor radon concentration depends on building materials like bricks, sands, cements, etc. Indoor radon has been recognized as one of the health hazards for mankind because long-term exposure to radon increases the risk of developing lung cancer. Therefore, the emission of the radon from building materials is important. To count these values, "CAN" technique and alpha sensitive LR-115 type II plastic track detector has been employed. After the exposure time of 100 days, all detectors were etched with 2.5N NaOH solution and tracks were counted under an optical microscope. From the obtained results, the radon concentration from gravel is the highest and its average value is $(218.99 \pm 23.71) \text{ Bqm}^{-3}$ but the value of ceiling shera board $(26.40 \pm 5.87) \text{ Bqm}^{-3}$ is the lowest value compared to other studied samples. In general, the values of the emission of radon concentration from studied building materials samples are below the safe limit as recommended by ICRP.

Keywords: Radon concentration, building materials, CAN technique, LR-115 type II plastic track detector

Introduction

Radiation plays an important role in our daily life as the world is naturally radioactive. People are exposed to ionizing radiation from naturally occurring radionuclides that are present in the building materials, water, fly ash, soil, etc. The rate at which radon escapes from samples into the surrounding air is known as radon exhalation rate of that samples.

The building materials such as bricks, sands, cements, etc., used for the construction of houses and buildings originate from different rocks and under water. Different naturally occurring radioactive elements are often riched in such building materials. Concentrations of present radionuclides in building materials vary depending upon the local geological conditions. Ionizing radiation levels in buildings related to radionuclide content in building material sample is essential in the assessment of population exposures because most of the residents spend about 80% of their lifetime in indoor air.

Radon is an invisible, odorless, tasteless and radioactive gas. The half-life of radon is 3.8 days. It is formed by the disintegration of radium, which is a decay product of uranium. Alpha particles and several solid radioactive products called radon daughters or "progeny" are emitted by radon. Radon progeny are inhaled with air and deposit in the lungs. The lung absorbs alpha particles emitted by the radon progeny. The resulting radiation dose increases the risk of lung cancer. Indoor radon concentrations are almost always higher than outdoor concentrations. Once inside a building, the radon cannot easily escape. International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) classifies radon as Group 1, carcinogenic to humans without smoking.

Materials and Methods

To measure the radon concentration alpha sensitive LR-115 Type II plastic track detectors commonly known as Solid State Nuclear Track Detectors (SSNTDs) were used. In

* Dr., Associate Professor, Department of Physics, Bago University

** Dr., Lecturer, Department of Physics, Bago University

*** Assistant Lecturer, Department of Physics, Bago University

**** Dr., Demonstrator, Department of Physics, Bago University

this research, “CAN” method has been employed for the measurement of radon concentration from some building materials samples. Sand, gravel, red brick, black cement, white cement, floor tile, wall tile, ceiling shera board and gneiss were collected for my research. Twelve samples were collected from local market at Yangon Division and three samples were collected from Nyaung Lay Bin. The collected samples were crushed, dried and powdered. Each powdered samples were weighted 140 g with sliding balance. Then known amount of each samples were put inside the cylindrical plastic can. Each alpha sensitive LR-115 Type II plastic track detectors of size (1 cm × 1 cm) were fixed on the bottom of the lid of each can with cello tape such that the sensitive side of the detector faced the samples. The cans were tightly closed from the top and sealed. The geometrical parameters of the container were 8 cm in diameter and 11 cm in height. The exposure time of all detectors were 100 days. The schematic diagram of the “CAN” technique for measurement of radon content in some building material samples is shown in figure 1.

After exposure time, each detectors were removed and subjected to a chemical etching process in 2.5 N NaOH solutions at $(60 \pm 1)^\circ\text{C}$ for 90 min. The etching system is shown in figure 2. After etching, the detectors were washed with water until the surface of the detector became cleaned from etchant. Then, the rinsed detectors were dried with filter paper. Etched tracks show as bright holes in a dark red background, and are very clearly visible under the optical microscope of magnification $10\times - 100\times$. In this work, track counting was performed by using OLYMPUS BX51 optical microscope with $20\times$ magnification attached with monitor and camera control unit. OLYMPUS BX51 optical microscope is shown in figure 3. Only tracks that have been completely perforated the sensitive layer have been counted. The number of tracks viewed on the monitor were counted view by view changing the vertical and the horizontal position of detector under the microscope. The track density of each sample was calculated by using the track density equation:

$$\text{Track density, } \rho(\text{ track cm}^{-2}) = \frac{\text{Net number of tracks}}{\text{View field Area}}$$

Radon concentration in the samples was calculated using the following formula:

$$C_{\text{Rn}}(\text{ Bq m}^{-3}) = \frac{\rho}{\eta T}$$

Where η = the calibration coefficient of LR-115 detector, T = exposure time

Based upon the radon concentration measurement data, annual effective dose and exhalation rates were calculated using the following equations:

$$\text{For annual effective dose: } H_E(\text{ mSv y}^{-1}) = C_{\text{Rn}} \cdot D \cdot F \cdot T$$

Where D = the dose conversion factor, F = the indoor equilibrium factor between radon and its progeny, T = time

$$\text{For mass exhalation rate: } \text{MER}(\text{ mBq kg}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}) = \frac{C V \lambda}{M T_e}$$

$$\text{For surface exhalation rate: } \text{SER}(\text{ mBq m}^{-2}\text{ h}^{-1}) = \frac{C V \lambda}{A T_e}$$

Where C = integrated radon exposure, V = volume of the air in the can, A = area of the sample, λ = decay constant for radon, h = distance between the detector and the top of the sample, T_e = effective exposure time = $T - \lambda^{-1}(1 - e^{-\lambda T})$

Figure 1 The schematic diagram of the “CAN” technique for measurement of radon content in some building material samples

Figure 2 Etching system

Figure 3 OLYMPUS BX51 optical microscope and alpha tracks on the monitor

Results and Discussion

The calculated values of radon concentration, mass and surface exhalation rates and annual effective dose of some building materials are shown in table. From these results, the radon concentration from gravel is the highest while the lowest value is from ceiling shera board compared to other studied samples. The values of radon concentration for gravel ranged

from $(214.11 \pm 35.69) \text{ Bqm}^{-3}$ to $(223.88 \pm 11.73) \text{ Bqm}^{-3}$ and its average value is $(218.99 \pm 23.71) \text{ Bqm}^{-3}$. The average values of mass exhalation rate, surface exhalation rate and annual effective dose for gravel are $(4.10 \pm 0.44) \text{ mBqkg}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$, $(114.03 \pm 12.37) \text{ mBqm}^{-2}\text{h}^{-1}$ and $(6.90 \pm 0.75) \text{ mSv y}^{-1}$ respectively.

The values of radon concentration from sand ranged from $(170.11 \pm 13.20) \text{ Bqm}^{-3}$ to $(228.77 \pm 44.48) \text{ Bqm}^{-3}$ and its average value is $(199.44 \pm 25.58) \text{ Bqm}^{-3}$. The average values of mass exhalation rate, surface exhalation rate and annual effective dose for sand are $(3.53 \pm 0.45) \text{ mBqkg}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$, $(78.54 \pm 10.08) \text{ mBqm}^{-2}\text{h}^{-1}$ and $(6.29 \pm 0.81) \text{ mSv y}^{-1}$ respectively.

The values of radon concentration from red brick ranged from $(171.11 \pm 40.57) \text{ Bqm}^{-3}$ to $(175.00 \pm 31.77) \text{ Bqm}^{-3}$ and its average value is $(173.05 \pm 36.17) \text{ Bqm}^{-3}$. The average values of mass exhalation rate, surface exhalation rate and annual effective dose for red brick are $(2.16 \pm 0.44) \text{ mBqkg}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$, $(24.05 \pm 5.00) \text{ mBqm}^{-2}\text{h}^{-1}$ and $(5.46 \pm 1.14) \text{ mSv y}^{-1}$ respectively.

The values of radon concentration from black cement ranged from $(72.35 \pm 32.75) \text{ Bqm}^{-3}$ to $(101.68 \pm 28.84) \text{ Bqm}^{-3}$ and its average value is $(88.64 \pm 30.79) \text{ Bqm}^{-3}$. The average values of mass exhalation rate, surface exhalation rate and annual effective dose for black cement are $(1.47 \pm 0.51) \text{ mBqkg}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$, $(27.32 \pm 9.52) \text{ mBqm}^{-2}\text{h}^{-1}$ and $(2.79 \pm 0.97) \text{ mSv y}^{-1}$ respectively.

The values of radon concentration from ceiling shera board is $(26.40 \pm 5.87) \text{ Bqm}^{-3}$. The values of mass exhalation rate, surface exhalation rate and annual effective dose for ceiling shera board are $(0.41 \pm 0.09) \text{ mBqkg}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$, $(6.55 \pm 1.46) \text{ mBqm}^{-2}\text{h}^{-1}$ and $(0.83 \pm 0.18) \text{ mSv y}^{-1}$ respectively.

The values of radon concentration from white cement is $(47.90 \pm 21.02) \text{ Bqm}^{-3}$. The values of mass exhalation rate, surface exhalation rate and annual effective dose from white cement are $(0.79 \pm 0.35) \text{ mBqkg}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$, $(14.80 \pm 6.43) \text{ mBqm}^{-2}\text{h}^{-1}$ and $(1.51 \pm 0.66) \text{ mSv y}^{-1}$ respectively.

The values of radon concentration from floor tile is $(33.24 \pm 25.02) \text{ Bqm}^{-3}$. The values of mass exhalation rate, surface exhalation rate and annual effective dose from floor tile are $(0.59 \pm 0.44) \text{ mBqkg}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$, $(13.09 \pm 9.85) \text{ mBqm}^{-2}\text{h}^{-1}$ and $(1.05 \pm 0.80) \text{ mSv y}^{-1}$ respectively.

The values of radon concentration from wall tile is $(28.35 \pm 16.13) \text{ Bqm}^{-3}$. The values of mass exhalation rate, surface exhalation rate and annual effective dose for wall tile are $(0.50 \pm 0.28) \text{ mBqkg}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$, $(11.16 \pm 6.35) \text{ mBqm}^{-2}\text{h}^{-1}$ and $(0.89 \pm 0.51) \text{ mSv y}^{-1}$ respectively.

The values of radon concentration from gneiss is $(27.86 \pm 4.4) \text{ Bqm}^{-3}$. The values of mass exhalation rate, surface exhalation rate and annual effective dose for gneiss are $(0.52 \pm 0.08) \text{ mBqkg}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$, $(14.51 \pm 2.29) \text{ mBqm}^{-2}\text{h}^{-1}$ and $(0.88 \pm 0.14) \text{ mSv y}^{-1}$ respectively.

Figure 4 shows the variation of radon concentration and sample code from some building materials. From this figure, it can be seen that the amount of radon concentration from gravel is the highest and the lowest is ceiling shera board. From figure 5, the annual effective dose is directly proportional to the radon concentration for each sample.

Table Radon concentration, mass exhalation rate ,surface exhalation rate and annual effective dose from some building materials samples

Sr No.	Sample Code	Radon Concentration (Bq m ⁻³)	Mass Exhalation Rate (mBq kg ⁻¹ h ⁻¹)	Surface Exhalation Rate (mBq m ⁻² h ⁻¹)	Annual Effective Dose (mSv y ⁻¹)
1.	S1	228.77 ± 44.48	4.04 ± 0.79	90.06 ± 17.55	7.21 ± 1.40
2.	S2	170.11 ± 13.20	3.01 ± 0.23	66.97 ± 5.20	5.36 ± 0.42
3.	S3	199.44 ± 19.06	3.53 ± 0.34	78.58 ± 7.50	6.29 ± 0.60
4.	Gr1	214.11 ± 35.69	4.01 ± 0.67	111.54 ± 18.66	6.75 ± 1.13
5.	Gr2	223.88 ± 11.73	4.19 ± 0.22	116.53 ± 6.08	7.06 ± 0.37
6.	RB1	171.11 ± 40.57	2.14 ± 0.50	23.80 ± 5.61	5.40 ± 1.28
7.	RB2	175.00 ± 31.77	2.18 ± 0.39	24.31 ± 4.40	5.52 ± 1.00
8.	BC1	101.68 ± 28.84	1.69 ± 0.48	31.40 ± 8.88	3.21 ± 0.91
9.	BC2	91.9 ± 30.8	1.52 ± 0.51	28.31 ± 9.52	2.90 ± 0.97
10.	BC3	72.35 ± 32.75	1.20 ± 0.55	22.26 ± 10.16	2.28 ± 1.03
11.	WC	47.90 ± 21.02	0.79 ± 0.35	14.80 ± 6.43	1.51 ± 0.66
12.	FT	33.24 ± 25.02	0.59 ± 0.44	13.09 ± 9.85	1.05 ± 0.80
13.	WT	28.35 ± 16.13	0.50 ± 0.28	11.16 ± 6.35	0.89 ± 0.51
14.	CSB	26.40 ± 5.87	0.41 ± 0.09	6.55 ± 1.46	0.83 ± 0.18
15.	Gn	27.86 ± 4.4	0.52 ± 0.08	14.51 ± 2.29	0.88 ± 0.14

S = Sand, Gr = Gravel, RB = Red Brick, BC = Black Cement, WC = White Cement
 FT = Floor Tile, WT = Wall Tile, CSB = Ceiling Shera Board, Gn = Gneiss

Figure 4 Variation of radon concentration and sample name from some building materials

Figure 5 The relation between radon concentration and annual effective dose of some building materials

Conclusion

“CAN” technique and solid state nuclear track detectors are best suited for the measurement of radon concentration, mass exhalation rate, surface exhalation rate and annual effective dose from some building materials samples. The values of annual effective dose obtained are found to be linearly dependence with radon concentration. The amount of the emission of radon from the studied building materials are under the safe limit as recommended by ICRP. The International Commission on Radiological Protection recommended that the radon concentration for dwelling is from 200 to 600 Bqm⁻³. Thus, the results reveal that the studied building materials are safe for the health hazard effects of radon exhalation.

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my sincere thanks to Rector Dr Aye Aye Tun, Bago University for her encouragement to do this research work. I am deeply thanks to Dr Yin Yin Than, Pro-Rector, Bago University for her helpful advice and valuable guidance. I wish to express my sincere thanks to Professor Dr Khin Htoo, Head of Department of Physics, Bago University for her helpful advice and kind permission to carry out this research work.

References

- Khin Hlaing (2013) Investigation of Radon Concentration inside Some Caves in Hpa-an Township, Kayin State, Myanmar. PhD Thesis Physics Department, Yangon University
- RRJoP (2013) 10-19 © STM Journals 2013. All Rights Reserved
- World Journal of Nuclear Science and Technology, 2015, 5,141-148 Published Online July 2015 in SciRes.

http://www.ccohs.ca/oshanswers/phys_agents/radon.html